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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NARATRIPTAN HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

Kumara Swamy.G*¹, JMR.Kumar², J.V.L.N Sheshagiri Rao³, U.Ashok Kumar¹, Vidya sagar. P¹.

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Trinity College of Pharmaceutical sciences, Peddapalli, Karimnagar (dist) - 505172.A.P. India. ²Holy Mary Institute of Technology and Science (HITS), Ghatkesar, Hyderabad. ³College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam- 530 003, A.P, India

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ABSTRACT

A simple efficient, precise and accurate spectroscopic method has been developed and validated for quantitative estimation of Naratriptan Hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. Naratriptan is dissolved in distilled water and the resulting solution was then scanned in the UV range (200-400nm) in a 10 mm quartz cell in a double beam UV spectrophotometer. The λ_{max} of Naratriptan was found to be 223nm. The method obey's Beers law in the concentration range from 2-12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9998 ($r^2 = 0.9998$). The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.4362 and 1.3265 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The result of estimation of marketed tablet formulation (Amerge) was found to be 99.47% with their % RSD 0.4362. The accuracy of the method was determined by recovery studies. The percentage recovery was found to be 99.83%. The method was validated statistically as per ICH guidelines. The method showed good reproducibility and recovery with % RSD less than 2. So, the proposed method was found to be simple, specific, precise, accuracy, linear, and rugged. Hence it can be applied for routine analysis of Naratriptan in bulk drug and the Pharmaceutical formulations.

Corresponding author

Kumara Swamy.G
Email: kumaraswamy.gandla@gmail.com.
Mobile: +91- 9581972289

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INTRODUCTION

AMERGE Tablets contain naratriptan as the hydrochloride, which is a selective 5-hydroxytryptamine₁ receptor subtype agonist. Naratriptan hydrochloride is chemically designated as N-methyl-3-(1-methyl-4-piperidinyl)-1H-indole-5-ethanesulfonamide monohydrochloride. The review of literature revealed that no methods were reported for the estimation of Naratriptan in bulk and tablet formulations.

OBJECTIVE

To develop a simple, precise and accurate spectroscopic method for the estimation of Naratriptan in Pharmaceutical formulation. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines. Thus the objective of present study was developed and applicable for the routine analysis of Naratriptan in tablet formulations (Amerge 2.5mg tablets).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Instrumentation and analytical conditions:

The validated method utilized a Shimadzu UV-1800 UV/VIS spectrophotometer with 1cm matched quartz cells was used for spectral and absorbance measurements at ambient temperature. The absorbance was measured at 223 nm.

Stock and working standard solutions:

Weigh accurately 100mg of Naratriptan raw material was transferred into the 100 ml volumetric flask dissolved and made up to 100 ml with Distilled water. The solution was observed to contain 1000 µg/ ml and diluted to get 100 µg/ ml.

The above stock solution (0.5–3.0ml of 100µg/ ml) was transferred into six 25 ml volumetric flasks and made up to mark with Distilled water. The absorbances of resulting solutions were measured at 223nm using Distilled water as blank. Calibration curve was plotted by using concentration Vs absorbance. The curve was linear with the concentration range of 2-12 µg/ ml.

Assay of sample preparation:

Twenty commercial tablets (labeled concentration 2.5 mg of Amerge) were weighed and their mean mass was determined. After grinding the tablets into a fine powder in a glass mortar. 100 mg of equivalent Naratriptan

Fig.1 chemical structure of Naratriptan hydrochloride

Fig.2 UV Absorbance spectrum of Naratriptan

Fig 3. Calibration curve of Naratriptan

Table: 01 Recovery studies of Naratriptan

Amount Present (µg/ml)	Amount added* (µg/ml)	Amount found* (µg/ml)	% recovery *	Average ± S.D	% RSD
8.03	1	9.01	99.05	99.83± 0.4362	0.4396
8.03	2	10.06	101.50		
8.03	4	12.03	98.96		

Table 2: Intra-day and inter- day Precision of the method

Precision	Experimental con.(µg/ml)	Recovery (%)	*RSD (%)
1. Intra- day (n=6)	8.09	99.91	0.97
Inter -day			
1 Day (n=3)	8.23	99.86	0.73
2 Day (n=3)	8.15	99.47	0.85
3 Day(n=3)	8.03	98.95	0.91
Mean (n=9)	8.06	99.43	1.35

formulation was taken into a series of three 100 ml standard flasks. To that 1 mg, 2 mg and 4 mg of raw material were added in to series of standard flasks 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Dissolved with Distilled water and made up to volume with Distilled water .The solutions were sonicated for 10 minutes. After sonication, the solution was centrifuged at 100 rpm for 15min. The solutions were filtered through Whatmann filter paper No. 41.From each standard flask, 2 ml of the clear filtrate was transferred into a series of six 25 ml standard flasks and made up to volume with Distilled water. The amount of drug recovered was calculated. Each concentration was repeated for three times. Finally the method was validated as per ICH guide

lines for precision, accuracy, specificity, linearity, reproducibility, LOD and LOQ.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A simple, selective, accurate, precise spectroscopic method for the estimation of Naratriptan in bulk and tablet dosage form has been developed and validated. The linearity range in the concentration range of 2-12 µg/ ml ($r^2= 0.9998$).It indicated that the concentrations of Naratriptan had good linearity. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.4362 and 1.3265µg/ ml respectively. The amount of Naratriptan was calculated as 99.47%. Further the precision of the method was confirmed by the repeatable analysis of formulation. The percentage recovery was found to be in the range of 98.96-101.50%.The procedure was repeated for 3 times for each concentration. The % RSD was found to be 0.4362%.It indicated that the method has good precision. The low % RSD value indicated that there is no interference due to excipients used in formulation. Hence, the accuracy of the method was confirmed.

CONCLUSION

The proposed method is simple, accurate, precise and selective for the estimation of Naratriptan in bulk and in tablet dosage forms. The method is economical, rapid and do not require any sophisticated instruments contrast to chromatographic method. Hence it can be effectively applied for the routine analysis of Naratriptan in bulk and in tablet dosage forms.

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